

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF A COURT CASE
INFORMATION AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

BY

ADEBAYO, SULAIMON OLAWALE

169074142

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this project work is entirely the result of hard work, finding, exploration and enquires. I am confident that this project work is not copied from any other person. All sources of material and information have however been acknowledged with due respect.

Sulaimon Adebayo

Adebayo Sulaimon O.

12/07/2019

Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to notify that this research project “**Design and Implementation of a Court Case Information and Management System.**” submitted to the school of Postgraduate Studies, University of Lagos, for the award of Masters in In Information Technology is a record of original research carried out by Adebayo Sulaimon Olawale in the Department of Computer Sciences.

.....

Dr. O.A Sennaike

Project Supervisor

Date

APPROVED

Dr. O.B. Okunoye

Head of Department

Date

DEDICATION

This project work is dedicated to Almighty Allah the giver of wisdom, knowledge and understanding.

My sincere gratitude goes to the Department Head of Computer Science Dr. O. B. Okunoye, my supervisor Dr. O. Sennaiké and all other staff of the department for their continuous guidance and selfless dedication to the completion of this research work.

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ABSTRACT

One of the most important issues in various justice structures across the country is access and processing of an effective and efficient justice system. This can be traced back to the late 1880s when the Supreme Court of Lagos was institutionalized. The main functionalities carried out in court works are registration, routing of court data and information, indexing and follow up of cases. Case management is a key success factor in judicial systems. Efficient, organized and Systematic case management system provides comprehensive information for courts to guarantee unbiased decision and transparency information system to hinder the misuse of power or corruption, case postponement and delays in decision making. It also reflects the good image in judiciary.

This project illustrates the process involved in the design and implementation of a court case information and management system intended at addressing the lapses/manual processes in the mode of initiating and processing court cases as well as efficient storage management with timely retrieval of stored information. The main objective of this project is geared towards development of a web based platform where court cases related information are easily accessible as well as providing suitable information update procedures in a secured, collaborative and simple manner.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Chapter One	9
1.0 Introduction	9
1.1 Background.....	9
1.2 Statement of Problem	9
1.3 Aims and Objectives.....	10
1.4 Scope and Limitations	10
1.5 Significance of Study	10
1.6 Project Outline.....	10
Chapter Two	11
2.0 Literature Review	11
2.1 Overview	11
2.2 Effectiveness of Service Delivery in the Judiciary.....	11
2.3 Information Management System	11
2.4 Characteristics of an Information Management System	12
2.5 Component of Web Based Application.....	13
2.5.1 Hypertext Transfer Protocol	13
2.5.2 Web Server	13
2.5.3 Web Browser	13
2.6 Tools and Model.....	14
2.6.1 MVC Architecture	14
2.7 Database.....	16
2.8 Database Management Systems	16
2.9 Advantages and Disadvantages of DBMS	17
Chapter Three	18
3.0 Methodology	18
3.1 System Analysis.....	18
3.2 System Development Methodology.....	18
3.2.1 Requirement Discovery:	19

3.2.2	Problem Analysis:	19
3.3	System Requirement Analysis	20
3.4	Functional Requirement Analysis	20
3.5	Use Case Analysis	21
3.6	Entity Relationship Model (Database Modelling)	27
3.7	Database Storage Design	27
Chapter Four		30
4.0	System Design Specification	30
4.1	System Architecture	30
4.2	Database Design	32
4.2	Choice of Programming Tools	32
4.3	System Requirements	33
4.4	System Requirements	33
4.4.1	Software Requirements	33
4.4.2	Hardware Requirements	33
4.5	Operating Enviroment	34
4.6	Software Testing	34
Chapter Five		39
5.1	Summary	39
5.2	Achievements	39
5.3	Constraints and Limitations	39
5.4	Recommendation	40
5.5	Conclusion	41

TABLE OF FIGURES

Fig 2.1 Model – View- Controller Diagram	Pg. 14
Fig 2.2 Database Systems	Pg. 16
Fig 3.0 Waterfall Model	Pg. 19
Fig 3.1 System Administrator Use Case Diagram	Pg. 23
Fig 3.2 Case Management Officer Use Case Diagram	Pg. 24
Fig 3.3 Registrar Use Case Diagram	Pg. 25
Fig 3.4 Judges Use Case Diagram	Pg. 26
Fig 3.5 Entity relationship Diagram	Pg. 27
Fig 4.1 System Architecture Diagram	Pg. 30
Fig 4.2 Model – View- Controller Framework	Pg. 31
Fig 4.3 Home Page	Pg. 34
Fig 4.4 Landing Page for User Registration	Pg. 35
Fig 4.5 Landing Page for Case Management Officer	Pg. 36
Fig 4.6 New Case Registration Page	Pg. 36
Fig 4.7 Landing Page for Registrars	Pg. 37
Fig 4.8 Landing Page for Pending Cases List.....	Pg. 37
Fig 4.9 Login Page for Judges	Pg. 38
Fig 4.10 Landing Page for Judges	Pg. 38

TABLE OF FIGURES

Table 3.1 New Data Table	Pg. 26
Table 3.2 Cases Table	Pg. 26
Table 3.0 Users Table	Pg. 27

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) enabled processes are gaining necessary momentum in our day to day activities (i.e. existing eco-system). Internet based case management system allow users (plaintiff, accuser and requestor) to initiate a request against an entity, organization or government, monitor the flow of activities, assign specific functions and store relevant information as may be required. ICT, a *colonne vertebra* of several startups, local communities, international organizations and the least group of people that exist today.

The integration of web based tools for process handling has empowered several startups in managing specific functions such as banks payment handling, government tax processing, performing hospitality and treatment and processing stock management in stores and supermarkets. When we make payment for accrued taxes, we initiate an existing integration with a clearing organization (such as Remitta) rather than tax agents and the processing is carried out online real-time, with the opportunity of generating the required receipts.

Developed countries hinge largely on the implementation of Information and Communication Technology in handling and managing court cases (i.e. civil, criminal and other cases). This has led to successful implementation of remote courts, mobile courts, e-courts etc., where judgements are carried out, recorded and managed online. The web based solution system will enable Nigeria citizens to initiate and track court cases efficient and technology driven manner, provide case status, update, effective management and access to other cases using a generated case ID. The term court cases and court requests are used interchangeably in this research.

1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

In several cases, the plaintiff/accuser/requestor fails to catch up with relevant court cases and other necessary pre – court arrangements. This is due to irregular and inconsistent available information to the initiator of the court case from appropriate quarters. This leads to situations where access to information is based on chance or most times physical follow up (usually few/) by the case owner with the court register and lawyers leading to the following issues:

1. Late presentation of required information and documentations
2. Lack of coordinated planning by the lawyers and their respective clients
3. No track records to be referred to by court judges

This project is set to enable a controlled and complete case registration process for all activities to eliminate manual tasks and reduce turn around time. The System provides core functionality that is to offer meaningful supplementary benefits to the courts, such as more

efficient data entry, more effective data retrieval, better tools and enhanced public access, thus the public can have access to it anytime and anywhere

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this project is to develop a web based (information and client profile management system) application which will advance the existing method of information flow, dissemination and management during case handling during the course of case trial in a manner that minimizes process inefficiencies and unwarranted delay by clients, prosecutors, lawyers, court registers etc. This will address lapses in the existing method of sharing relevant information as well as reduce or eliminate manual access to client data profile through its information management system. It aim to allow lawyers and judges have access to client records during and after completion of the legal trial

The extended objective of this project work is as follows:

1. To create a system that will facilitate and effective information sharing system
2. The software will allow information to be entered by users, control information in the system and tracking of current case status to enhance public access.
3. The system “Event” and “Scheduling” is to determine new case arrivals, session appointments, case deadline, reservation of courtroom and the judge who will head the case
4. To provide an effective case information management platform that is easily accessible to all users i.e. allow plaintiff, accuser, accuse or requestor to access and update relevant information.
5. To improve collaboration between respective users through information sharing and discussions
6. To enhance direct communication of specific task information between the plaintiffs, accused, lawyers, judges and the court.

1.4 SCOPE AND LIMITATION

This research work aim to develop a web based system to receive and process initiated court cases, manage case profile, enhance case flows and collaboration through discussion and share of required information. Also create an enabling platform for judges to directly communicate with other participant in the case management process. Mail service management module will not be implemented though it will be part of our recommendation for this project.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The court case information management system is designed to enhance the legal system procedures to improve the existing process, access to relevant information and better engagement in a more collaborative manner.

This platform provides an automated handling of court cases and process management for the citizens of the Federal Republic of Nigeria to improve their engagement in a more efficient and collaborative system. This also gives access to searches, preview and rights to varieties of information regarding closed and ongoing cases.

1.6 PROJECT OUTLINE

The project report is categorized into five chapters. Chapter one introduces the problem statement and highlights how the precise problem will be addressed through the aims and objectives and it also contains the significance of this study. Chapter two concentrates on the review of literature and relevant research associated with the problems addressed in the study. Chapter three focuses on the methodology and procedures used for data collection and analysis, determining functional and non-functional requirements of such an application.

In chapter four, the section explains the areas of implementing and testing of various prototypes at different stages in the development and also contains the various techniques and languages used in the development process. Chapter five offers a summary and discussion of findings, present and future and recommendations for future research

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

The importance of achieving an effective and efficient system requires the identification of issues relating to the early judicial procedures and existing manual processes. This helps to carry out the best approach to attain the project goal based on the review. This segment concentrates on the global, African and Nigerian perspective in the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Integrated Court Management System in the delivery of an efficient justice

The restraints of the traditional methods of judicial system in Nigeria can only be solved by embracing the electronic justice system. Hence, Information and Communication Technology should be deployed in conducting functional activities in Nigerian Courts, considering its successful adoption in some other jurisdictions such as (United States, Malaysia, Japan and Philippines).

2.1 CONVENTIONAL PROCESS OF JUSTICE DELIVERY

It is very important to state that the judicial proceedings start long before a case reaches the court room. A civil action/criminal cause commences once a plaintiff and/or the plaintiff's lawyer submits a writ of summons or a complaint with the clerk of the court in any manner prescribed by the law. The administrative personnel of the courts file and keep registers and documents in compliance with the codes of procedures, laws and regulations (Adelowo Stephens & Halimat Akaje 2003).

Sequence of actions must align with the function above such as collation and formal control of the filed documents by the clerk of the court, documentation at the time of collecting relevant files, registration of the event on the court register and issuance of receipt to the plaintiff and/or the plaintiff's lawyer.

2.2 CONSTRAINTS OF CONVENTIONAL PROCESS OF JUSTICE DELIVERY

One fact about the conventional process of justice delivery in Nigerian courts is its time consuming and cumbersome features. This is because all case document is recorded, filed and distributed on papers. Yusuf Ali (2012) explained further that by conventional method, a litigant may wish to request for a copy of court proceedings, ruling and judgements; this request must be routed and addressed to the court through the court Registrars. Notwithstanding the purpose for which the request is need, the litigant will have to await the feedback of the court for the document to be prepared (typed, proofread and retyped).

In line with the above, the major issues/constraints of conventional justice delivery systems are as follows:

- Difficulty of filling Court Processes
- Inadequate Processing Tools and Equipment
- Insecurity of Court Documents
- Lack of Transparency
- Lack of Technical Know – How:

Finally, the influence of technology changes traditional ways of court case operations such as case filing, case fees, cause list etc. Legal information processed through technology tools becomes more and more important in comparison to traditional source.

2.3 INFORMATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

An information management system (IMS) is a general and applied term for a resource system used to process cases, facilitate storage and retrieval required for an effective organization management. With the great role played by Information Management Systems in any organization or country, IMS creates affluence on the function, productivity and performance of such organizations. This is a platform used for efficient planning, controlling and finalizing critical decisions making process. This system is made up of the software, hardware, data, telecommunication and the users.

2.4 COMPONENTS OF WEB BASED APPLICATION

A web based solution is an application that can be accessed by its users through the internet/intranet or specialized user agents. The developer creates an HTTP request for a defined URLs that map to specific resources on the Web Server. The server receives, renders and return the required HTML page to the CLIENT (i.e. requesting PC, system or agents) which the browser can display. This embodies a client – server application program, in which the clients runs in the browser (Nations, Daniel, 2014).

The server side logic represents the core of the web application. The web application can contain several layers such as the presentation layer, logic layer and the data layer. The presentation layer formats and present data to the in an accurate, unique, standardized and well – defined manner. This layer includes character code translation, data conversion, data encryption and decryption and data translation.

The logic layer manages the inter connection and information transfer between an end user interface and the system database. This logic regulates how data and information are created, archived and changed. The logic layer separates the presentation layer from the data layer and regulates the information flow and data exchange between the two layers.

The data layer is the protocol that manages the set of information available on the web page. This information contains any data that are might be transmitted to other systems, soft wares or application

2.5 TOOLS AND MODELS

2.5.1 MVC ARCHITECTURE

MVC stands for Model – View – Controller which promotes organized programming by separating application functionality. It is one of the most frequently used software architectural patterns for general web frameworks. Each of the MVC components are built to handle specific development aspect of an application.

Fig 2.1 Model – View – Controller Diagram

(Source <http://www.mundointerativo.com/2017/09/08/how-learn-mvc-architecture-design-patterns/>)

❖ MODEL

The model is major responsible for getting and manipulating the data (also referred to as the brain of the application). The model has the following features listed below:

- Data Related Logic
- Interactions with Database (DB)
- Communicates with CONTROLLER
- Can sometimes update the VIEW (depending on the framework)

❖ VIEW

This controls the actual view of the application. This can be the application user interface and/or what user sees when interacting with the application. The VIEW components/features consist of the following:

- The User Interface (UI)
- Usually consist of HTML/CSS
- Communicates with the CONTROLLER
- Can be passed dynamic values from the controller
- Template Engine

❖ CONTROLLER

This acts as a connector/intermediary between the MODEL and t VIEW components. This processes all the business logic and incoming requests, manipulates data using the Model components and renders the final output using the View components. Some of the actions carried out by the controller are listed below:

- Receives Input (from view, URL)
- Processes Request (GET, POST, DELETE, PUT)
- Get data from the MODEL
- Processes data to the VIEW

2.6 DATABASE

This is a structure of data stored in an organized way representing user/system data or information. This can be stored or accessed using a computer system. The features and component of a basic database are Row, Column, Table and Schema.

- Row – This is a representation of data using the row models as we have in spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel)
- Column – the distinct set of data are displayed by the column structure of a data set. Several types of data are contained in each column such as alphanumeric data, integer data and character value etc.
- Table – This contains multiple columns containing distinctive data form. A table can contain as little as two (2) columns and the size of a table depends on the distinctive data types being stored.
- Schema – one or more schema forms a database. This is the collection of one or more tables of data or information.

The information is stored, managed, updated and retrieved using database management systems. This has been applied in so many day to day activities such as websites libraries, schools, supermarkets etc.

2.7 DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (DBMS)

DBMS can be further simplified to the equation below:

DBMS = Database + Management System.

This can be defined as a set of inter related data and collection of programs to manipulate, store and manage those data in a structured set. This simplifies the process of declaring, defining, building, influencing and sharing databases among several clients and solutions. A Database Management Systems is a 4th Generation Language such as Oracle, SQL Server, Mongo DB and MS Access etc.

Fig 2.2 Database Systems

2.8 ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF DBMS

The DBMS have several advantages and disadvantages as highlighted below:

ADVANTAGES:

- Reduction of redundancies
- Shared data
- Data Integrity
- Security
- Data Independence

DISADVANTAGES

- Cost
- Complexity of backup and recovery
- Problem with centralization

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 METHODOLOGY

A methodology is a process used to organize the theoretical analysis, systemic procedures showing all important part of a research method and principles associated with a defined solution to a question in study. This section details how the research was planned, assessed and executed the research methods used and the reason for choosing the highlighted methods.

3.1 SYSTEM ANALYSIS

Several analysis were carried out to highlights the genesis of existing problem. This were achieved when users or administrators start studying the behavioral pattern of the program using the existing system. In the analysis process, key activities were carried out such as data collections, decision made on critical problem and processes handled by the existing system. Several tools were used carrying out the analysis such as Entity Relationship diagram (ERD), Unified Modeling and Analysis, Data flow Diagram (DFD), flow chart and problem algorithms.

Efficient software development process depends majorly on the quality of the problem analysis applied prior to development and properly dealing with the required stages. The characteristics of software or a program development informs the techniques to be deployed for the design and other rules that are required to be followed when designing the required solution.

3.2 DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGY

The requirement team expectations and the inherent features determine the relevant software methodology. For the purpose of this project, we chose the Waterfall Model for its simplicity and understanding. In this approach, the whole process of developing the required software is divided into separate phases. In Waterfall model, the outcome of one phase acts as the input of the next phase sequentially.

The phases of waterfall model are: Requirements, Design, Implementation, Testing/Deployment and Maintenance

Fig 3.0 Waterfall Model

3.2.1 REQUIREMENT DEFINITION

The intended solution is a web based (i.e. online) system that will handle all forms of court cases registration, profiling, updates and dissemination of information in an efficient and collaborative manner.

3.2.2 PROBLEM ANALYSIS

The identified problem is to develop a web application which improves court cases processing, management and easy access to registered users. To provide an effective solution, the problem has been divided into sub – problems so as to facilitate easy resolution. This can then be integrated into a complete working application.

1. Landing Page
2. Online Login
3. Submission of relevant information
4. Routing of posted information (from one user to another)
5. Assignment of relevant privileges
6. Management of posted information
7. Display of relevant notification to show successful processing or otherwise
8. Display of different function classification

At the Login module, the username and password credentials should be validated accurately at the time of Login for all users and administrators. User credentials are identified uniquely by the name of the entity using the solution, while admin account is identified by their unique ID (i.e. **ADMIN**) and relevant password.

3.3 REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS

The developed system should have the capacity to process the following:

1. Allow user to Login with their registered username and password
2. Allow ADMINS to login with their required user name and password
3. Maintain data associated with all cases
 - A user data has unique ID (Username) and password as well as other important fields such as Name, E-mail, and Profile_Image etc.
4. Allow Admins to create a new case, provide relevant information and store them accordingly
5. Maintain information record for separate case session
6. Allow users (i.e. Registrars) to view all cases created by the administrators
7. Allow only admins to access the case management function
8. Users (i.e. Judges) must be able to view and update all assigned cases

3.4 FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS

The solution will present a number of capabilities. During the system requirement analysis phase, we identified certain users called ACTORS. These actors are case management officers, registrars, judges and system administrators.

The functional requirements are as shown below:

1. Login Module: This shall be developed to have a centralized rights and authentication facility to ensure only authorized users have access to the system providing a security standard to protect vital information.
2. Adding and Removing Cases: This will provide the registrar the authority to add new cases and to terminate cases if they pass away.
3. A Database Facility: This shall be developed to store, record, information about users, (date, suit number, plaintiff, defendant, judge etc.)
4. Edit or Update Module: This shall be developed to ensure easy corrections of mistakes. Only registrar can access this feature.
5. Reporting Facility: At the end of every day's activities a report will be printed out. So as to keep track of events.
6. Backup: This shall be developed to backup data periodically.

3.5 NON-FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS

Non-functional requirement describes how a system should behave and what limits there are on its functionality.

1. Performance: The system shall allow several case registrations at the same time without downgrading performance.
2. Availability: The system shall be available to all court and can be access anywhere.
3. Usability: The system shall be easy to learn and use by all users including registrar and administrator.
4. Reliability: The system has low system failure occurrence and low risk. And will not take much time to resolve it.

5. Accuracy: The system shall work accurately without high failure or error.
6. Security: each user is required to login. The system shall allow people with assigned user names and passwords. The system shall be designed to make it impossible for unauthorized people to logon without valid usernames or password.

3.6 USE CASE ANALYSIS

The analysis below depicts the use case description of the assigned functions carried out on the system

Use Case Name: Login/Authenticate – Use Case

Initializing actors: Administrators, Case Management Officers, Registrars, Judges

Pre-condition: None

Description: ` This authenticates the actors to have permission to interact with the personalized case management system.

Steps:

Type the address or navigate to login page

Enter login credentials i.e. username and password

Post Condition: Actor is taken to appropriate landing page

Benefiting Actors: System Admin

Use Case Name: Register New Court Case – Use Case

Initializing actors: Case Management Officers

Pre-condition: Actors must have logged into the Case Management Module

Description: ` This creates a new case form, where the actor can provide relevant case information, upload the required image and submit.

Steps:

Click Case Management Office button on the homepage

Enter login credentials i.e. username and password

System displays the New Case Form

Fill the available fields

Click submit to store all information provided by the actor

Post Condition: Actor is taken to appropriate *home* landing page

Benefiting Actors: Case Management Officers, System Admin

Use Case Name: View Court Case – Use Case

Initializing actors: Registrars

Pre-condition: Actors must have logged into the Registrars Module of the Case Management System

Description: ` This module displays all cases initiated by the Case Management Officer. This also displays all relevant information and the link to the specified address where the image is stored.

Steps: Click Registrar button on the homepage
Enter login credentials i.e. username and password
System displays the table containing the list of all initiated cases
Click *back* button for system to redirect the actor to the homepage.

Post Condition: Actor is taken to appropriate *Home* landing page

Benefiting Actors: Case Management Officers, System Admin

Use Case Name: Update Court Case – Use Case

Initializing actors: Judges

Pre-condition: Actors must have logged into the Actor's Module of the Case Management System

Description: ` This module displays all cases initiated by the Case Management Officer. This also displays all relevant information and the link to preview the image. Actors can also update the case status.

Steps: Click Judge Button on the homepage
Enter login credentials i.e. username and password
System redirects user to the landing page
System displays the list of all initiated and approved cases

Click *the text image* button to update the existing information on the verdict column in the Database

Post Condition: Actor is taken to appropriate *Home* landing page

Benefiting Actors: Case Management Officers, System Admin

SYSTEM ADMIN USE CASE DIAGRAM

Fig 3.1 System Admin Use Case Diagram

CASE MANAGEMENT OFFICER USE CASE DIAGRAM

Fig 3.2 Case Management Officer Use Case Diagram

REGISTRAR USE CASE DIAGRAM

Fig 3.3 Registrar Use Case Diagram

JUDGES USE CASE DIAGRAM

Fig 3.4 Judges Use Case Diagram

3.7 DATABASE DESIGN

A database structure (otherwise known as schema) is the skeletal composition that represents the logical view of the entire database. It defines how the data is arranged and how the relations among them are associated. It formulates all the constraints that are to be applied on the data.

The schema is proprietarily maintained and controlled by the database administrator/user and has the same name as that user. Each user has owned a single schema. There are three levels of database schema thus:

1. **Conceptual Schema:** is a map that conceptualizes business needs at a high level showing its concepts and their relationships. This is a process of producing a description (in high level terms) of the contents of a Database DB system. The process represents input information requirements provided by the application interacting with the database to a required schema displayed in conceptual modeling notation. Such as Extended Entity Relationship model, Unified Markup Language class diagrams etc.
2. **Logical Schema:** This can be referred to as the end user view of the database structure characterized by tables. It is a map of entities, their relationships and attributes. This depicts the database information according to the data model of implementation language. This is where each table of the columns is defined. This also models the existing business requirements
3. **Physical Schema:** This represents the final blueprint of a logical schema. This show the physical mode of data storage on a system hard drive. This considers and accurate use of data types for entity columns and avoiding system reserved words for defining entities and columns. All constraints to design must be properly clarified. Such as primary key, foreign keys etc.

3.8 ENTITY – RELATIONSHIP MODEL (DATA MODELLING)

The entity relationship model (also known as ER model) is a distinct type of data modeling technique tailored for designing a relational database. This model focuses on two major components i.e. the data entity of a business ecosystem to be modeled, the relationship between the entities and the exhibiting attributes (i.e. the properties of each entities and its relationship).

The model entails the use of a relative technique to document a system software or solution using diagrams and symbols. It depicts how each entity are related to one another.

Fig 3.5 Entity Relationship Diagram

3.9 DATABASE STORAGE DESIGN

Data persistency is one key focus of this project and this is part of what informed our choice of deploying a relational database system. Below is the schema of the system which includes the required rows and columns, tables, relationship attributes and/or properties.

The tables below display relevant information about each actor in the proposed solution.

Table Name: *Newdata*

#	Name	Type
1	Id	Int(5)
2	SurName	Varchar(50)
3	Last_Name	Varchar(100)
4	Email	Varchar(100)
5	PhoneNo	Varchar(20)
6	UserName	Varchar(10)
7	Password	Varchar(10)
8	DateTime	Varchar(10)

Table 3.1: Newdata Table

Table Name: Cases

#	Name	Type
1	<i>Id</i>	<i>Int(5)</i>
2	<i>Court</i>	<i>Varchar(50)</i>
3	<i>CourtRoom</i>	<i>Varchar(100)</i>
4	<i>CaseNo</i>	<i>Varchar(100)</i>
5	<i>SurName</i>	<i>Varchar(20)</i>
6	<i>Other</i>	<i>Varchar(10)</i>
7	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Varchar(10)</i>
8	<i>Offence</i>	<i>Varchar(10)</i>
9	<i>No_Hearing</i>	<i>Int(1)</i>
10	<i>Age</i>	<i>Int(10)</i>
11	<i>Last</i>	<i>Varchar(30)</i>
12	<i>AHR</i>	<i>Varchar(30)</i>
13	<i>Verdict</i>	<i>Varchar(200)</i>
14	<i>Passport</i>	<i>Varchar(100)</i>
15	<i>Address</i>	<i>Varchar(100)</i>
16	<i>Origin</i>	<i>Varchar(100)</i>
17	<i>Lawyer</i>	<i>Varchar(10)</i>
18	<i>Datetime</i>	<i>Varchar(50)</i>

Table 3.2: Cases Table

Table Name: Users

#	Name	Type
1	<i>Id</i>	<i>Int(5)</i>
2	<i>Username</i>	<i>Varchar(50)</i>
3	<i>Name</i>	<i>Varchar(100)</i>
4	<i>Email</i>	<i>Varchar(100)</i>
5	<i>Password</i>	<i>Varchar(20)</i>

Table 3.3: Users Table

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

4.0 SYSTEM SPECIFICATION

The solution architecture used in this project explicitly described all relevant features and attributes. Considering the scope of the project, a three tier architecture (i.e. a client – server architecture) was adopted which enable users to interface the functional logic, data storage and defines the control for accessing relevant data.

These functions or separate architecture tiers are developed and maintained as independent modules built in different platforms. This also facilitates an individual system to undergo specific upgrade without disrupting the activities of other tiers of system.

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system based case management system uses architecture; comparison of three independent tiers as shown in the figure below.it can be noticed that the architecture contains the functional business module, the database module and the data access module

Fig 4.1: System Architecture

The functional business logic can be further divided into the presentation layer and business layer. Each layer performs unique function and encourages reusable system functionalities. The relationship between each module is mutual. Information are also exchanged between modules in carrying out a specific task.

For a user to initiate a case on the portal, the presentation layer offers a user interface to the user enabling them to provide relevant information about the case. The business layer serves as the mechanism that is responsible for processing the user's request received via the

available interface. The data storage and data access layer serves as a repository of all the data and/or information used in the processing using the developed system. It also allows users to add, query, call and update new/existing information and carry out other related processes and/or activities.

4.2 CHOICE OF PROGRAMMING TOOLS

- **User Interface**

This is a part of the solution that enables human-computer interaction. This was developed by Hypertext Markup Language (HTML), JavaScript (Js) and Cascading Style Sheet (CSS). The input and out forms were designed by HTML and Js, while CSS was used for styling of the forms and the appearance of the webpages. Flex was used to achieve webpages responsiveness across all devices

- **Relational Database Management System**

This is a system used to create, configure, edit, structure, alter and delete database entities, their relationships and attributes. MySQL was used as the relational database management system (RDBMS) for this project. This was installed on the local sever machine with default username and password.

- **Local Web Application Server**

These are remote computers, local computers or computer programs that convey web information (such as web pages, etc.) to the end user through an active internet connection upon request via a web browser. It includes a computer system and a server program. For the purpose of this project, WAMPSEVER application was used to serve as the *localhost* (i.e. the web server)

- **Web Browser(s)**

These are solutions (i.e. software applications) that can be used by end users to retrieve and display web pages and contents from the World Wide Web and /or Internet. These browsers run on different operating systems to access the internet. Examples are Google Chrome, Safari X, Microsoft Edge, Internet explorer etc. All this browsers listed above can be used for running the case management system project.

4.3 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

The requirement for this project is sub categorized into two namely:

1. Software requirements
2. Hardware requirements

4.3.1 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

The project was developed as a result of integrating several open source solution frameworks. The combination of these frameworks to work for a single purpose has been the major resulting outcome of this project.

Client Side:

Web browser, Windows 10 (or other latest versions), Unix, Linux, MAC OS

Web Server:

Web browser, Windows 10 (or other latest versions), Unix, Linux, MAC OS

Server Side:

- JavaScript
- PHP
- WAMP
- MySQL

4.3.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

Client Side:

Web browser, Windows 10 (or other latest versions), Unix, Linux, MAC OS

Processor:

Pentium 2.0 or higher

Random Access Memory:

512 MB or more

Server Side:

Operating System of Windows 10 (or other latest versions), Unix, Linux, MAC OS

Processor:

Pentium 2.0 or higher

Random Access Memory:

512 MB or more

Hard Drive:

5GB or more

Others:

Monitor: Any monitor capable of displaying the signal sent by the customer.

Keyboard:

A standard QWERTY keyboard for data entering.

Web browser (Chrome, Firefox, Internet Explorer and Microsoft Edge)

Local Area Network or Internet Connection, Mouse etc.

4.4 OPERATING ENVIROMENT

The software will be a web powered solution, which means that it was deployed and tested by a web browser. This solution should be able to run on a client server, a system on an internet connection or locally on a web server. This decision will be based on the location of the webserver

When the data is stored locally, then the solution will run locally. This means that the solution and the data reside on a local system. The external interface will be through the browser with HTML as the markup language, PHP and JavaScript for scripting and CSS for page formatting.

4.5 SOFTWARE TESTING

The project was tested in order to find out and correct possible errors. These errors range from operational testing, unit testing, system testing, user acceptance testing etc. These tests were conducted prior to the installation and deployment of the new project.

Figure 4.3: Home Page

Application software was installed and/or loaded on existing or new hardware, while several users were introduced to the new solution. Integration tests accesses whether a set of modules or programs that must work together do so without error.

The figure above represent the home/index page of the web based application. This is the default page that is presented when the application link is first clicked. This page presents three sub modules which are: Case Management Office, Registrar and Judge Modules. The

figure below shows the module for registering new users. This module is designed for administrators, where they can add a new user, provide relevant information and store the details provided in the **USERS** db.

Fig 4.4 Landing Page for User Registration

The password will be encrypted by the system using HASH data security (SHA-256 algorithm). This enable the data provided for the password to be converted to several string combinations stored in the database.

The figure below shows the landing page for the case management officers. The page enables the officers to access the **new request form** when they have successfully logged on with a valid credentials to initiate a new case and assign to the respective court room. The page also allows the users to access the **register new user page** where new user information can be stored on relevant database table.

Fig 4.5 Login Page for Case Management Officers

The figure below shows a **Register New Case** form, where users provide relevant information about the plaintiff, assigned case number, select court and courtroom and provide lawyer’s information. Users will store the provided information in the designed database by clicking the submit button. Once successful, the page will redirect the user back to the homepage.

Fig 4.6 New Case Registration Page

The figure below shows the login page for REGISTRARS to enable them access the required information assigned to them. Users provide relevant username and password and system validates the information when the login button is clicked. Users also have access to reroute to the register new user landing page. The home button allows the users to redirect the page to the default home page.

Fig 4.7 Login Page for Registrars

The pending cases list highlights relevant information on all registered cases submitted by the Case management Officer. This can be viewed only by registered REGISTRARS whose information is stored on the user database

Fig 4.8 Landing Page for Pending Cases List

Fig 4.9 Login Page for Judges

The figure above displays the login page designed for the registered JUDGES and validates provided information against the information available in the *users db*. If the login is successful, the system automatically loads the pending cases for the JUDGES (see image below).

Fig 4.10 Landing Page for Judges

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 SUMMARY

The project work has outlined how system processes can be adopted to enhance and ensure proper management of court case information systems. This also allows efficient dissemination of information and storage of relevant processing data.

The first chapter handles the general overview of the project which includes background of study, aims and objectives, methodology and the significance of the project. It also highlights the statement of problem and outlined the required solution.

The second chapter dealt with the evaluation of relevant literature on project history and court case information management system and an overview of the proposed project as defined in this document. This chapter also listed the advantages of previous system and evaluated various components of a web based application technologies, system and other tools used in development.

The third and fourth chapters explain the applicable software development processes that were used for this project work. This ranges from requirement gathering and analysis, solution design and development, project testing and implementation. While the last chapter handles the conclusions and required recommendations.

5.2 ACHIEVEMENTS

The quest to make life easier and enhance the processing of data and information has led to virtually integrating all works of life with information and communication technology. Computer and information technology have transformed various ways of life, most especially the educational sector through mobile learning, access to timely information and improved virtual learning.

The achievement of this project is that it will improve the management of court cases through all relevant process owners. It will also enhance access to case data/information, dissemination of such information and encourage more users of the project work. This solution will go a long way to address the cause of delays in processing court cases and routing of such cases to relevant users in a structured and well managed manner.

5.3 CONSTRAINTS AND LIMITATIONS

While working on this project, some constraints were encountered which ranges from designing the required Database (DB), Tables and Images and other relevant information. Some issues were observed when designing the E-R Diagram, such as Microsoft Word application used for the project documentation does not have the required shape needed for designing the Entity Relationship diagram. This was eventually designed using another solution and then import the information to Ms. Word

Also, I encountered some issues in designing the physical DB schema. This is solely because the Microsoft word used for documentation does not support some technical drawings. Limited resources (i.e. available materials) to aid prompt development of required input to

the project work is another constraint. Lastly, time is another important constraint encountered during the course of this project. The time spent in carrying out this project work was very limited. Regardless of the limited time, the project was carried out with commitment and precisions.

5.4 RECOMMENDATION

The project work has been developed to address some identified key issue, this can be upgraded to include a mailing and or notification systems. Also a plaintiff should be able to initiate his/her cases in their comfort homes/office. A search and indexing function should be added to project work to enable easy lookup of relevant file and information

5.5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, from proper assessment and adequate analysis of the proposed system it can be safely concluded that the system is a dependable, usable and efficient Case Management System. It was tested and working properly and the design meet the minimum solution requirements. The solution will function as an electronic repository system that facilitates engagements and collaboration among the users (i.e. the Admins, Case Management officer, Court Registrar and the Court Judges).

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